

BEAT ESTIMATION FROM MUSICIAN VISUAL CUES

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ABSTRACT

Musical performance is an expressive art form where musicians interact with each other using auditory and non-verbal information. This paper aims to discover a robust technique that can identify musical phases (beats) through visual cues derived from a musician's body movements captured through camera sensors. A multi-instrumental dataset was used to carry out a comparative study of two different approaches: (a) motiongram, and (b) pose-estimation, to detect phase from body sway. Decomposition and filtering algorithms were used to clean and fuse multiple signals. The final representations were analysed from which estimates of the beat, based on a 'trust factor', were obtained. The Motiongram and pose estimation were found to demonstrate usefulness depending on the musical instrument as some instrument playing gestures stimulate more movement in the players than others. Overall, the results were most promising using motiongram. It performed well where string instruments were used. The spatial derivative technique based on human pose estimation was consistent with woodwind instruments, where only a small degree of motion was observed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human bodies typically move along to musical rhythms and studies conducted on infants have shown that already at such a young age there is a strong sensory link between body movement and auditory rhythm processing [1]. When people listen to musical performances, their mind subconsciously starts participating with it. Audience members can be seen to respond by tapping their feet, clapping their hands, or nodding their head. Musicians also move their body in different ways to perform expressive pieces depending upon the instruments they are playing. These movements enable them to express and portray their musical ideas [2], and their body movements have a significant effect on musical rhythm perception. Understanding the underlying dynamics of this strong correlation between music and movement has been identified as an important component within the music, art, and engineering interdisciplinary field [3]. Non-verbal gestures and movements

also provide musicians with a strongly connected communication between each member of the ensemble during performance as well as the audience. The interaction adds a unique and immediate dimension to a live performance that is unavailable from a recording. There is a constant transfer of information through the expressive movements of the musicians during the performance offering an integrated auditory and visual experience. Wanderley et. al, [4] studied the performances of five clarinetists to analyze the significance of gesture in three different ways: immobile, standard and expressive. The results of this experiment emphasized the presence of ancillary gestures which were consistent throughout the performance and were an integral part of musical performances. It is difficult to get musicians to perform completely still and change ingrained movements. Conscious and unconscious movements by musicians are made during the performance to make the performance look natural and expressive.

There exists a large computational complexity in correctly decoding musical cues from body movements using video data, and so it still remains a challenging task [5] [6]. Additionally, accuracy in identification is not obtained easily. In this paper, we focus on analysing the connection between musicians' body movements and the associated audio rhythms. We evaluated the performance of two different approaches to understand and predict rhythmic phases or beats from multiple musician's while they are performing. The method developed offers a general representation and approach that is independent of the number of instruments and musicians.

2. RELATED WORK

There are some examples in the literature of multi-modal methods of ascertaining the rhythm of a performance, that is, by not analysing the musical signal alone, and incorporating other information sources. As might be expected, the wide availability of video encourages the use of gestural cues but others have taken more novel perspectives. In the category of novel is a very recent study by [7] on Indian Classical Dance. Here, the music of the dancing combined with features extracted using speech processing techniques were analysed for rhythm marking.

Intuitively, it is expected that there should be a correlation between gestural behaviour and the rhythm of a performance. However, the connection is not fully understood. Some work has been put into furthering our understanding, others have looked at synthesizing gestural and audio

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data. In the former case, preliminary findings have been obtained regarding the manifestation of period and phase-locking behaviour in full-body movements associated with how people participate in music. [8]. More comprehensive measurements of whole-body movement were also made. In the study of [2], the freedom of use of the head and upper body in the movements of pianists were examined along with their relationship to the performance. To better understand how to synthesize a convincing interaction between movement and sound, animation and video manipulation have been used. A method based on pixel motion sonification was introduced by [9]. Its success led to the analytical tool known as the Motiongram (to be discussed in Section 4). In the study [10], they did a similar manipulation of an animation. They used an LSTM network, trained using the input sound signal (piano and violin) along with measured gestures, to estimate the positions (termed as body keypoints) on an animated skeleton. This was the first time such a procedure was attempted using these keypoint features, and the demo was rated as working well. Similarly, Liu et al. [5] involved the recreation of violinists' body movements from music recordings and videos. Improvements and additions were made to the machine learning model to account for the finger positions and the orientation of the 3D skeleton. Kao and Su [3] generated a model formed in a U-net based encoder architecture, that included two additional network architectures created for the body and the right hand, and a self-attention mechanism. This was used to animate a virtual violinist's skeletal movements in 3D synchronized with a music signal. Moving away from animations, Davis and Agrawala [11] studied visual rhythm from videos, seeking associated features that are manifested in the temporal dynamics of the visible motion. They applied this to develop a novel way for manipulating actual performances in a dance video, keeping the movement and audio in synchronization. Lastly, in tandem with this thread in the research, other authors have focused on creating better beat tracking algorithms and analysis by including gestural cues. An audio-visual rhythm analysis was carried out by tracking body skeleton features detected using a Kinect sensor combined with the audio signals in [12]. They fused the video and audio data using a 'tempo likelihood' to create a predictor for the tempo and beat. It was reported that the video cues outperformed the traditional audio beat tracking in a noisy environment in the tempo prediction. To summarise, mixing gestural and audio data would improve beat and rhythm estimation. However, the method to do this is not fully established. This paper will contribute by developing algorithms that can work on features derived from representations of performances extracted from video. The next section introduces the dataset and the experimental setup. The following section goes through the methodology, explaining the Motiongram and pose estimation representations and the features extracted from them. There is a set of results presented along with a discussion. The paper ends with some conclusions and recommendations for future work.

Figure 1. Example of the Midi and Audio representations (left and right panel respectively) used for their alignment to determine the beats

3. DATASET AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We used an audio visual multi-instrument dataset, which contains 44 full musical performances [13]. The dataset is ideal for this experiment as the musical tracks had a significant tempo and clearly observable musical leader-follower exchanges unlike a typical live orchestra. As later in part 5, we evaluate on fugue composition where a short phrase is successively introduced from multiple musicians behaving as a 'lead', while others 'follow' the cue. The dataset contains four major types of performances: 11 Duets, 12 Trios, 14 Quartets, 7 Quintets.

For this study, three random videos were selected from each of the sections. The dataset also provided the audio, MIDI, and musical notations of each performance used to generate the ground truth.

3.1 Finding The Audio Beat

To understand musical phases, the time of the audio beats are important. The audio beats were considered as the ground truth value in our experiment. To compute audio beats, an audio-MIDI alignment technique was used [14]. As shown in Fig 1, the MIDI file representation (left hand side) was converted to its equivalent audio (right hand side). Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) was applied to effectively match and align the music recordings with the corresponding MIDI transcriptions. After which, the beats were estimated from the aligned-MIDI information. This process was repeated for the whole dataset.

4. METHODOLOGY

For estimating the musical phases of the video signal, firstly the video needed to be converted into a 1-D time-series signal. Two different approaches were used to identify a robust and scalable representation with respect to the number of musicians in the frame. In this experiment we used the following:

4.1 Video to Motion Signal

To convert the videos to a signal representing motion, we investigated two different approaches. They were :

Figure 2. Three signals generated from motiongram data of a video (a), X : Horizontal motion, Y : Vertical motion, Z : Quantity of motion (b) The three X , Y and Z motion signals with the time instances of the audio beat superimposed on them

4.1.1 Motiongram

The motiongram was created by calculating the spatio-temporal motion using the average pixel intensity change between frames of video. It provides a series of images showing motion in two dimensions across the image plane, I with dimensions $n \times m$, for some small time-step dt , see Equation 1. The signals generated with respect to the motiongram are shown in Fig 2. In the plot in the upper panel the X -value refers to the average horizontal pixel positions in the image, while the Y -value refers to the average vertical pixel positions. The other feature used was the 'quantity of motion' [15], that represented the overall average amount of motion at that time-step. The signals were normalized independently for further processing. The lower panel shows the relationship between the X , Y and Z signals and the locations of the beats in the music. Change in number of participants was found to not effect the output of motiongram.

$$I(t + dt) = |I(x, y, t + dt) - I(x, y, t)| \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m} \quad (1)$$

4.1.2 Pose Estimation

Recognizing human activities from video sequences is a challenging task. While humans can do this easily, it is a more complex process for computers to recognize human activities efficiently, and such operations are based on multimodal activity recognition methods [16]. The pose estimation algorithm extracted the 2D coordinates of human body joint locations (such as arms, head) from videos.

To use pose estimation, we considered each musician as an individual oscillator. The average body movements generated by each of them was interpreted as a 1D motion signal. We used openpose, an improved and robust model pose estimation model that applies Part Affinity Fields (PAFs) to predict body keypoints for multiple humans [17]. These coordinates were used to compute the full body motion for each musician. It generated, 17 body keypoints, \mathcal{K} , from each frame of the video. The inter-keypoint distance of each individual was recorded over time from their body-center.

Two different approaches were tested with pose estimation. They are :

- First Frame as Reference
- Spatial Derivative of keypoints

In the first technique, the first frame was considered as the point of reference for calculating the motion. An average value was computed to find the relative motion resulting in a 1D signal for each musician as shown in the lower panel of Fig 3. This measured the variances of the keypoints for each time-step, see Equation 2¹ where $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is each keypoint, \bar{k} is the keypoint average, and n is the number of keypoints $\in \mathcal{K}$. Each musician was considered as an individual signal source. Therefore, with the increase in number of participants, there were more signals present.

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n L_2(k_i, \bar{k})}{n} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

The spatial derivative was used in the second technique to generate the average motion signal of each individual by comparing each frame's keypoints \mathcal{K}_t with its previous frame, similar to optical flow [18]. Given that the points had already been localized, there was no need to calculate the intensity-based image gradients. The spatial derivative, Δk , was calculated for each keypoint $\in \mathcal{K}_t$ using Equation 3, where k is each keypoint on the image plane. To get a measurement of how much motion was associated with each keypoint at time-step dt , the magnitude of the vector Δk was calculated, and an overall average μ_t for all the keypoints Δk_i at that time-step n was found, as given in Equation 4.

$$\Delta k = k(t + dt) - k(t) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_t(\Delta \mathcal{K}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \|\Delta k_i\|}{n} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4)$$

4.2 Post Processing

4.2.1 Filtering the signal

The signals generated by motiongram and pose estimator showed a rhythmic pattern when they were plotted. The Okada filter was used for smoothing the dataset [19]. This was used as it can increase the data precision without distorting or affecting the position of the signal peak. It is

¹ $L_2(\cdot, \cdot)$ represents the L_2 norm between two points or the Euclidean distance

Figure 3. The upper panel shows a frame of the video of the musicians where each musician represents as an oscillator and the lower frame gives the average motion calculated by pose estimation on each musician based on the first frame as reference and the spatial derivative of keypoints from each participants

based on logistic function over a single continuous differentiable equation as shown in Equation 5. Here, x_t refers signal value(x) at time t and x_{t-1} and x_{t+1} are at the previous and next time points respectively. α is a weighting factor and is typically set to be 100.

$$x_t \leftarrow x_t + \frac{x_{t-1} + x_{t+1} - 2x_t}{2(1 + e^{-\alpha(x_t - x_{t-1})}(x_t - x_{t+1}))} \quad (5)$$

4.2.2 Matrix Decomposition

We considered each signal as a dimension. Thus, using a matrix decomposition algorithm, we converted multiple signals into a single dimension. This one dimensional signal showed a high correlation with the audio beats (ground truth). We investigated five different dimensional reduction algorithms [20]. These included :

- Incremental principal components analysis (IPCA)
- Principal component analysis (PCA)
- Kernel Principal component analysis (KPCA)
- Dimensionality reduction using truncated SVD (aka LSA)
- FastICA: a fast algorithm for Independent Component Analysis

The multi-collinearity was handled by removing the redundant features. In Fig 4, the five dimension reduced signals were used for both motiongram and pose estimation output. The motiongrams horizontal(x-value), vertical image plane values(y-value) and quantity of motion(QOM-Value) were decomposed together, as shown in Fig 4(a). However, during these performances, there were multiple musicians interacting with each other. The body keypoints of each musician was considered as an individual independent oscillator generating a signal. For example, in a quartet performance, four average motion signals were treated

Figure 4. 1D signals generated after dimensional reduction of the motion signals with five different algorithms (a) Three dimensions (X, Y, QoM) of motiongram were reduced to one-dimensional signal (b) Reduced one-dimensional signals obtained from multiple musicians' pose estimated motion

as four different dimensions. Additionally, matrix factorization techniques were used to combine the movement data as a single oscillator for phase prediction.

4.2.3 Peak and Valley Detection

Each decomposed signal provided its own set of timestamps. A peak detection algorithm [21] was used to detect the peaks and the valleys for each of the five decomposed signals. The peaks and valleys were then merged and sorted in increasing order of time. The times of all the five signals were superimposed on each other. A voting-based system was used for selecting phases. Any three of the signals providing matching timestamps at their peaks/valleys were considered (following cut off thresholds). Other peaks/valleys were ignored. Strong points were considered to be visual beats and compared with the audio beats (ground truth) as shown in Fig 5.

5. RESULTS

For the evaluation² we selected three from each of the four types of performance, as shown in Table 1 which had not been used for the training. The classical pieces were composed by renowned composers including Holst, Mozart, Joplin, Bach and others. The preference for classical music is that it is often performed with rubato and thus its tempo more elastic than the beat-driven pop or rock music. In addition to this, beat detection can be difficult for instruments of the string, brass, and wind family as their onsets are less well-defined when not played in a percussive style. Overall, this detection problem is exacerbated by the absence of drums in most classical music. The musical pieces were selected in such a way so that all types of musical instru-

² <https://github.com/SutirthaChakraborty/motiongramVsPoseEstimation>

Figure 5. To calculate the phase of the movements, (a) Peaks and (b) Valleys were detected from dimensional reduced signals and are shown by red crosses in the upper and lower panels respectively.

ment were included in the experiment, and thus we could precisely identify the impact of the instruments' family on the accuracy of the two different approaches used for the video to signal conversion. Musicians can often exhibit an instrument-specific style of movement that helps them to maintain the rhythm while playing [22]. For computational accuracy when making the evaluation, we considered two cases: Firstly, that the beats that were exactly predicted by the algorithms and secondly, that the beats that lay within a bound of 100ms on either side of the ground truth beat's timestamp. The value of 100ms was chosen as since the videos are 29.75 frames per second (FPS), it means within three video frames either side of the audio beat event there must be a corresponding video beat event [23]. On executing the evaluation, we found that the best detection approach depends mostly on the types of instrument played and on the number of musicians playing, as shown in Fig 6. During validation, we achieved a maximum F1-score of 0.34 when using the motiongram, followed by a score of 0.33 when using optical flow to predict the audio beats of each performance. The First Frame Reference approach had the worst result of 0.32. The full validation results are shown in table 2. In Fig 6 the Motiongram output values (shown by the blue bars) were found to be most distinct for string instruments. This was expected as the musicians exhibit greater levels of activity while playing. In contrast, the pose estimation with the optical flow method worked well with woodwind instruments as those musicians display minimal motion. Considering all the instrument families, the Motiongram was found to be more reliable overall and yielded a more consistent performance with an increase in the number of musician participants. We also

Type of Performance	Name	Duration	Instrument*	Total Beats
Duet	Jupiter	01:03	Vn,Vc	86
	Sonata	00:46	Vn,Vn	44
	The Entertainer	01:27	Tpt,Tpt	216
Trio	Spring for the Four Seasons	00:35	Vn,Vn,Vc	65
	Hark the Herald Angels	00:47	Vn,Vn,Va	88
	Waltz from Sleeping Beauty	01:33	Fl,Fl,Cl	304
Quartets	Pirates of the Aegean	00:50	Vn,Vn,Va,Vc	163
	Pirates of the Aegean	00:50	Vn,Vn,Va,Sax	163
	In the Hall of Mountain King	01:25	Vn,Vn,Va,Vc	160
Quintets	Miserere Mei Deus	00:40	Fl,Fl,Ob,Cl,Bn	87
	Miserere Mei Deus	00:40	Fl,Fl,Ob,Cl,Bn	86
	Chorale	00:53	Tpt,Tpt,Hn,Tba,Tba	144

*Instruments : Vn=Violin, Vc=Cello, Tpt= Trumpet, Va= Viola, Fl=Flute, Ob=Oboe, Cl=Clarinet, Bn=Bassoon, Tba= Tuba

Table 1. Performances selected for evaluation

	Motiongram	First Frame Reference	Optical Flow
F1-Score	0.34	0.32	0.33
Precision	0.35	0.34	0.33
Recall	0.32	0.30	0.31

Table 2. Validation Score

found that musicians frequently tend to move their body in anticipation of the beat [24]. While not performing as well as the Motiongram overall the optical flow approach was reasonably consistent in its output, as can be seen in the figure. The pose estimation approach, where we considered the first frame as the reference frame, did not make reliable predictions as observed by the varying nature of the values plotted in Fig 6.

Figure 6. The evaluation procedure was carried out on 12 performances to find Fig (a): Quantity of Exact Matches: the ground truth audio phase matched with predicted phase from videos Fig (b): Quantity of Close matches: acceptable lag of the audio phase that is 100ms second apart from the predicted video phase.

6. CONCLUSION

This study shows how rhythmic phases could be predicted from a music ensemble or group performance using only video cues. Although difficult for the human eye to ascertain consistently, this approach could identify poten-

tially consistent features from the non-verbal communication that exists among musicians and how their body and gestural movements are engaged in maintaining the phase synchronization across beats during a musical performance. The study considered how the physical playing activity could be considered as oscillators and how this could characterise the underlying rhythmic dynamics of their body movements. We presented a promising set of techniques for predicting the beat locations utilizing data derived from a video recordings of the musicians' bodies. We can conclude from our results that the approach is influenced heavily by the instruments that are being played. If the instruments allow or encourage more movement during playing, such as string instruments, motiongrams and pose estimation combined with an optical flow technique would be more appropriate for predicting the musical rhythm. Pose estimation alone was more effective with instruments that inspire less body movement, such as those of the woodwind family.

For future work, the most immediate concern is to improve the accuracy by developing a post-processing technique that will eliminate sources of error that lead to false positives. Another idea is to develop a multimodal approach that fuses the predictions derived from the audio and video data. Also, at a higher level it would be useful to have an automated decision-making system that would simply choose the most appropriate analysis technique by identifying the music instrument type from the audio signal. In the longer term, video footage of larger ensembles of instruments will be studied, more data will be collected, and a greater use of machine learning technologies will be made.

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